

Bioassays demonstrated that Central Java populations could feed and reproduce on Cisadane, Krueg Aceh, and Sadang as readily as on susceptible Pelita I/1, but not on IR36, IR42, and IR54 (Fig. 1). Inability to feed on ASD 7 clearly distinguishes Central Java populations from biotype 3 (Fig. 2). Central Java populations were characterized by selective virulence on a certain group of varieties with the BPH resistance gene *bph 2* and were distinct from North Sumatra populations, which can infest all varieties with the *bph 2* gene. Such differences in virulence between Central Java and North Sumatra populations corresponded to the level of BPH resistance in the varieties on which both populations developed.

This indicates that BPH populations are able to modify their biotypic makeup in accordance with quantitative

2. Honeydew excreted on ASD7 by adult females of Yogyakarta populations collected from 4 different places, and Bogor biotypes 1, 2, and 3 maintained on Pelita I/1, IR26, and ASD7, respectively.

as well as qualitative variations of genetic resistance in host varieties to maximize their fitness values. Central

Java populations pose a problem with nomenclature of **BPH** biotypes in the field. □

Artificial diet for rearing rice leafroller (LF)

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Several artificial diets for lepidopteran insects were evaluated for rearing LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* (Guenée). A modified velvetbean caterpillar commercial diet was the most suitable. The diet consisted of 1,500 ml water,

17.5 g agar, and 230 g dry mix.

Six to eight grams of the diet was placed in a clear plastic cup (4.5 cm long, 4 cm diam) and baked in a 35°C oven for 24 h to evaporate excess water (too much humidity in the cup was found to be detrimental to survival of first-instar larvae). Two newly emerged first-instar larvae of *C. medinalis* were released in each cup and the cups covered with snug-fitting lids. The cups with larvae were inverted in an incubator at 27 ± 2°C, 65-70% relative humidity, and 12:12 photoperiod (see figure). Survival and growth of the insect were monitored daily, and compared with insect growth on 30-d-old susceptible IR36 rice plants.

Larval development on this diet (14-21 d, 16.2 d average) was almost the same as on IR36 plants (17 d). The percentage of larvae completing development was also quite high (93%). Average pupal weight was 21.02 mg, compared with 17.8 mg on IR36 plants. Average longevity of males (8.3 d) and females (9.6 d) was similar to that of insects reared on susceptible rice plants (7.8 and 9.3 d). Average fecundity of females reared on the artificial diet (182 eggs/female) was similar to that of

Rearing rice LF on an artificial diet. a) Inverted clear plastic cups with artificial diet, b) LF larva feeding on the diet, c) LF pupa in the plastic cup, and d) a LF pupa and an adult developed on the diet. IIRRI, 1987.

females reared on IR36 rice plants (163 eggs/female). We will be studying LF growth, development, longevity, and reproduction on this artificial diet for several generations. □

Effect of insecticides on rice gall midge (GM) and its parasite *Platyaster* sp.

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We studied the effect of three granular and three liquid insecticides on GM and the occurrence of its parasite *Platyaster* sp. during 1986 wet season. Treatments were applied 35 d after transplanting. GM incidence (% affected tillers) was estimated 20 d after treatment (DAT). Parasite occurrence was estimated 30 DAT by calculating percentage of puparia parasitized.

GM incidence was significantly lowest with carbofuran 3 G treatment, which was on par with chlorpyrifos 40 EC,

Effect of insecticides on GM and its parasite *Platyaster* sp. Madurai, India, 1986 wet season.

Treatment	Formulation ^a (%)	Dose (kg ai/ha)	GM incidence (%) 20 DAT ^b	Parasitization (%) 30 DAT ^c
Chlorpyrifos	10 G	1.0	8.4 (2.87)	90.0 (75.0)
Cartap	4 G	1.5	5.8 (2.38)	60.0 (50.8)
Carbofuran	3 G	1.0	3.8 (1.95)	60.0 (50.8)
Chlorpyrifos	40 EC	0.5	4.4 (2.07)	53.0 (46.9)
Monocrotophos	36 WSC	0.25	5.4 (2.26)	76.0 (61.2)
Phosalone	35 EC	0.5	9.9 (3.12)	80.0 (63.4)
Control	-	-	14.5 (3.77)	86.0 (68.8)
CD (P = 0.05)			(0.6)	(6.7)

^aG = granule, EC = emulsifiable concentrate, WSC = water-soluble concentrate. ^bFigures in parentheses are *x* values. ^cFigures in parentheses are arc sine values.

monocrotophos 36 WSC, and cartap 4 G (see table). Percentage of parasitization was lowest with chlorpyrifos 40 EC, which was on par with carbofuran 3 G and cartap 4 G. The insecticides effective on GM were toxic to the parasite. The highest

percentage of parasitization was recorded with chlorpyrifos 10 G, indicating that it is safe for the parasite; the EC of the same insecticide recorded the lowest percentage of parasitization, indicating that it is highly toxic to the parasite. □

Toxicity of five insecticides to the cricket *Metioche vittaticollis* (Stal) (Orthoptera: Gryllidae), a predator of some insect pests of rice

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The use of selective insecticides is important to protect the natural enemies of insect pests of rice. We studied the toxicity of some commonly used insecticides to *M. vittaticollis*, a predatory cricket in ricefields.

Test compounds from different groups of chemicals were used: BPMC, buprofezin, carbosulfan, monocrotophos, and cypermethrin. Insecticides were applied topically using a microapplicator. Mortality was recorded 24 h after treatment.

Based on LD₅₀ (μg/g), the order of decreasing toxicity of the 5 insecticides to *M. vittaticollis* was cypermethrin > carbosulfan > monocrotophos >

Toxicity^a of 5 insecticides to *M. vittaticollis*. IRRI insectary, 1985.

Insecticide ^b	LD ₅₀ (after 24 h)	
	μg/g	μg/insect
BPMC	4.51 (3.433-5.833)	0.05416 (0.0412-0.0700)
Monocrotophos	0.4008 (0.316-0.500)	0.00481 (0.00380-0.00601)
Cypermethrin	0.1442 (0.109-0.184)	0.00173 (0.00131-0.00221)
Carbosulfan	0.2308 (0.164-0.300)	0.00277 (0.00197-0.00361)
Buprofezin	>41,667	>500

^aFiducial limits in parentheses. ^bCalculated as ED₅₀ (the dosage that will give 50% mortality and abnormalities of the test animals).

BPMC > buprofezin (see table). The growth inhibitor buprofezin was not toxic and did not affect the molting of *M. vittaticollis* nymphs.

These results suggest that using selective chemicals such as buprofezin will conserve important biological control agents such as *M. vittaticollis*. □

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